

I. Service classes

A: Technical service	<p>A service of this type provides a technical and organisational solution that typically includes storage and computing services, software, processes and workflows, as well as the necessary personnel support for various service desks. NFDI4Objects services of this type must either be hosted on the Research Data Commons (RDC) reference implementation or provided by a partner organisation.</p> <p>The technical sustainability of the service must be ensured by an institutional organisation as service provider.</p>
B: Community-related service	<p>A service of this type ensures the structured organisation and content moderation of a community discourse on the development, updating and documentation of standards, best practices and workflows. The results are made available in sustainable and generally accessible solutions.</p> <p>The organisational sustainability of the service must be ensured either by an institutional organisation or by self-organised community groups as service providers.</p>

II. Service categories

Consortium services	<p>The services offered by member institutions of the consortium that have been evaluated in a structured process and meet the quality criteria adopted by N4O, including support from the consortium's central helpdesk.</p>
Partner services	<p>Relevant services that complement the consortium services, which are technically and organisationally independent of them. The services must be open for use by the community and can be offered by both N4O member institutions and other institutions.</p>

III. Types of service components

Web application	<p>Software that is installed on a server and can be used by users via a website on the Internet.</p>
Tool/client application	<p>Software that can be downloaded and run locally on the user's hardware.</p>
Database	<p>Software that provides users with large amounts of structured data. As a rule, this data can be uploaded, accessed, searched, edited and/or downloaded via a client or web browser.</p>
Workflow / Pipeline	<p>Software that combines several tools/applications. It can be used locally or remotely via the Internet.</p>
Library / API	<p>A collection of pre-implemented functions for a specific task that can be accessed via a precisely defined interface.</p>

Support / Advice	Service with direct user contact for issues that go beyond the support provided by other services.
Data curation	A service that supports the processes of organising, cleaning, reviewing and maintaining data sets to ensure their quality, reliability, findability and usability for current and future analytical or scientific purposes.
Training and education	(self-explanatory)
Storage	Provision of storage space for research data as a service for external users. Access is possible via Webprotokol.
Community management	A service that includes the active coordination and strategic support of specialist communities. This type of service component promotes exchange between members, moderates discussions and creates networking opportunities. The aim is to increase the participation of various specialist communities in the creation and further development of services and content and to present the results in a way that attracts public attention.
Content Creation	A service that develops, evaluates and monitors standards, best practices and workflows in collaboration with professional communities. In addition, all necessary resources (such as practical guides and training materials) that help to apply and implement these results in different working environments are developed and provided.

IV. Other definitions

Service providers	All actors who offer services or resources (such as data, metadata, publications, software, community management, etc.) resp. open up their own existing infrastructures or develop their tools in line with the general objectives and basic quality criteria of the NFDI in accordance with the research data lifecycle.
Service profile	The service profile contains all information about a service that is required for the use, operation or (further) development of the service. It is usually created by the service provider and, if necessary, quality assured by the service monitoring team as part of service portfolio management during onboarding or recertification.
Pre-Alpha	Service in initialisation and internal development. Feature requirements and use case queries may still be ongoing. Serves to provide advance notice and information to the community.
Alpha	First release with core features implemented. No user support, but bug reporting is possible.
Beta	Broad functionality, bug support available, documentation may still be missing.
Final release	Stable, fully functional version. Support and feature request option available. Documentation complete, including feature

releases. Only services with release status are certifiable.

Initialised

The service has begun its development work. Community services are in the development phase.

Consolidated

The development group has been formed. Processes and workflows have been established and results are publicly visible.